

THE ARTISTIC-AESTHETIC FUNCTION OF NOMINATIVE, INFINITIVE AND VOCATIVE SENTENCES AND THEIR PLACE IN ARTISTIC TEXTS

Erkinova Maftuna Elmurod qizi

3rd year student of Andijan State University, Faculty of Philology

Abstract: It is known that the concept of a sentence is inextricably linked with the concept of person, number, and time. Also for nominative sentences this idea should be applied. In existing literature, intonation completeness is shown as the basis for the formation of a word or phrase in a sentence.

Key words: nominative sentence, infinitive sentence, vocative sentence, apostrophe, emotions.

INTRADUCTION

One of the main features of the sentence is intonation completeness. But it is the most important another sign is predicativeness. And predicativeness is not without concepts of person-number and time. From a philosophical point of view what action takes place at a certain time.

MAIN PART

So, the concept of time is reflected in nominative sentences is enough. But the tense of the nominative sentence is before that or related to the tense of the sentence that follows will be They mostly exist in modern times subject, represents events (Nominative sentences do not have a negative form, if used with a negative form, its character changes. Nominative sentences are often expressive because they are short, concise and descriptive in nature. Nominative sentences to artistic style characteristic, serving as a separate stylistic tool does. Nominative clauses and the associated landscape are sometimes so impressive that it seems as if both the reader and the writer feel as if they are directly participating in that scene.

It is known that nominative sentences are divided into two types depending on their logical-grammatical characteristics. Availability and demonstrative sentences. To sentences expressing existence expressivity in expressive sentences will be strong.

There are many ways in which sentences are called infinitives similar to nominative sentences. The main difference between them is complement and case expansion or non-expansion. Since the name of the action is a verb form, it is natural that the sentence expressed by this word expands with case and complement. This feature is nominative not specific to the sentence. There is another difference between the two sentences in their scope. There are a lot of nominative sentences in speech,

especially in artistic language infinitive sentences are rarely used. Nominative and infinitive sentences from each other with respect to subtractive signs, their unifier, that is, there are many signs of similarity. The clause used after infinitive clauses is mostly in the form of a rhetorical question, or a direct protest, means anger or joy, joy. This case of infinitive sentences is strongly emotional shows that it has an expressive character.

In terms of structure, vocative sentences do not differ from imperatives. Therefore, cases of mixing vocative sentences sometimes with imperative, and sometimes with nominative sentences are visible. However, vocative sentences are distinguished by the fact that they reflect all the signs characteristic of a sentence, and they differ from the nominative sentence by the meaning they express. That is, nominative sentences are subjects and events such meanings as confirmation of existence, showing vocative sentences express feelings and emotions.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The main function of nominative sentences is speech emotionality, expressiveness is to serve for imagery. In general, infinitive sentences are short, concise speech forms that express the speaker's subjective view of reality reflects a strong emotional state. This type of sentence is not a separate form of a one-syllabic sentence, but a form that differs from a nominative sentence by some features.

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